

Analysis of Coping Mechanisms by Emancipated Women to combat Household Food Security in Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero, Uganda

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Abstract

Different groups have developed coping mechanisms towards combating household food security. The mechanisms to combat food security/ insecurity remain a necessity for all. Analysis of techniques or unique behavior by different groups amounts to coping strategies. Understanding the implemented coping strategies at household level is critical for formulating and implementing appropriate policy and design programs related to food insecurity. Despite these generalizations, there exists a gap in specific discourses that attempt to address coping mechanisms especially emancipated women in combating household food security/ insecurity which this study endeavours to fill by a focus on Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero, Uganda. This study used two objectives; analyzing coping mechanisms by emancipated women to combat household food security in Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero and examining whether Women Empowerment leads to a positive attitude towards household food security in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero to come up with findings from a primary research which can be applied in similar environments. This research underpins itself to The Resilience theory which is propounded by psychologists who affirm that individuals do not just emerge in adversity to fair well in their undertakings especially women in developing countries. They must be psychologically prodded in order to attain an attitude that makes emancipation possible. The study employed descriptive research design with both qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis being conducted in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero district, found in central Uganda. A sample size was 380 households drawn from Yamane (1967) formula. The researchers used both questionnaires and interviews to collect data. Data analysis of data was done both quantitatively and qualitatively. In its conclusions, determining how to build on and use women's knowledge base so that modern technologies can benefit from it and strengthen women's efforts remains a problem. Therefore the researcher recommends; exposure of more women to matters of land as a source of wealth and investment, need to train women on post harvest management and value addition for food preservation and better prices when selling, adopt irrigation to enable all year round farming, and use of better food storage

Keywords: Emancipated Women/ Women Empowerment/ Empowered Women/ Coping Mechanisms/ Food Security/ Household Food Security/ Kalagala/ Luweero/ Uganda

1.1 Introduction and Background to the Study

The issue of food security prompts households to reportedly exhibit a range of coping techniques that reflects their vulnerability (Kyaw, 2009). In the phase of idiosyncratic shocks such as food price hike or natural disasters, households may employ food or non-food based coping strategy or a combination of both to protect their basic needs (Ruel et'al, 2010; Food U, Organization A., 2008). In recently conducted studies, several coping strategies were found to be associated with household food insecurity, food consumption at household and individual level. Poverty measures as income and expenditure and seasonal variation of staple food production are also related to coping strategies (Ayieko and Midikila, 2010). Previous experiences have indicated that, during idiosyncratic shocks such as food price hike, poor households adopt a series of coping strategies which can be differentiated as food and non-food based techniques. Purchasing less preferred food, reducing meal size, consuming only rice, skipping meals and selling of assets were the frequently reported responses at the time of food shortage (Fintrac Inc., 2014).

A number of countries in Africa have gone through the devastating experience of effects of household food insecurity. For instance, Cameroon in West Africa, Egypt in Northern Africa, Ethiopia in the Eastern Africa and South Africa in the extreme Southern Africa. The World Food Programme (WFP) describes Cameroon as a

food insecure country, and has further demonstrated that food intake in households is lower now than in the early 1980s. The result of this is that 19% of young children in the country are underweight and child mortality rate is rising rather than falling. Ethiopia experiences serious household food insecurity. Over 7 million people out of Ethiopia's population of 76.9 million people are classified as food insecure; and a further 10 million people are identified as prone to drought. (Oneworld.net (US), 2009).

Chu (2009) points, Egypt produces half of its demand for wheat. In spite of the average food production, the country is exposed to the escalating food prices due to its wheat imports. It is classified as the number one importer of the produce in the world. Household food insecurity in Kenya is caused by inadequate farming area. It is only 18% of Kenya's territory which is suitable for farming. Another cause is poverty. The 2007/08 United Nations Human Development Report noted that almost 24% of Kenyans are living on less than one dollar a day, therefore not food sustaining (CBS, 2009). The World Food Programme reported that 50% of farmers were not sufficiently prepared for farming due to the post election turmoil. In addition, erratic rainfall exacerbates household food insecurity in the country. Poor rains in 1996 prompted the GOK to declare a state of national disaster on January the 28th (IRIN Humanitarian Report, 1997).

1.2 Problem Statement

Coping mechanisms to combat food security/ insecurity is a necessity for all. In connection to food insecurity, analysis of techniques or unique behavior executed by different groups translate to coping strategies. The household resilience to food insecurity reminiscences through fairly regular behavioral responses called coping strategies. They can be seen during crises moments when the resources are limited or absent, coping strategies work at specific stages of food insecurity because at some point if not rectified, the ability to cope might never exist. Literatures have identified (Helen Keller International (HKI), (2013)) diverse coping strategies applied at the household level amongst population affected by natural calamity and food price shock, but not in a general population who also tend to cope at a regular basis due to food insecurity at the household level. Particularly the contexts that compel households to apply only food compromised or financial coping strategies, are not well defined. Based on data collected through the food security and nutrition surveillance project (FSNSP), the single surveillance system in Bangladesh to look upon the coping behaviors of food insecure households countrywide. It is the thinking that understanding the implemented coping strategies at household level is critical for formulating and implementing appropriate policy and design programs related to food insecurity. Despite these generalizations, there exists a gap in specific discourses that attempt to address coping mechanisms especially emancipated women in combating household food security/ insecurity which this study endeavours to fill by a focus on Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero, Uganda.

Study Objectives

This study applied the following objectives in fulfilling its purpose;

- i. To analyze coping mechanisms by emancipated women to combat household food security in Kalagala Sub-County of Luweero.
- ii. To examine whether Women Empowerment leads to a positive attitude towards household food security in Kalagala sub-county of Luweero.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive research design with both qualitative and quantitative methods of analysis being conducted in Kalagala sub-county of Luwero district, found in central Uganda. A sample size was 380 households drawn from Yamane (1967) formula. The researchers used both questionnaires and interviews to collect data. Data analysis of data was done both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Theoretical Framework

This study underpins itself to The Resilience theory which is propounded by psychologists. To them it is the process of, capacity for, or outcome of successful adaption despite challenging or threatening circumstances. It is also defined as a predication on exposure to significant threat or adversity, and on the attainment of good outcomes despite this exposure. In relating the theory with women emancipation, this theory thus looks at

process involved. These include individual coping strategies, or assistance from peer empowerment groups, families efforts, schools and learning institutions, communities, and government policies that make resilience more likely to occur.

From the outset, resilience research pioneers, such as Norman Garmezy, Lois Murphy, Michael Rutter, and Emmy Werner, sought to inform practice by understanding the processes that explained how some individuals fared well in the face of adversity while others floundered (Masten, 2013). Their compelling ideas and research propagated the field of resilience science, which has transformed frameworks for practice in multiple disciplines by shifting the emphasis away from deficit-focused orientations toward models centered on positive aims, promotive and protective factors, and adaptive capacities (Masten, 2011).

The proponents of the theory aver that individuals do not just emerge in adversity to fair well in their undertakings especially women in developing countries. They must be psychologically prodded in order to attain an attitude that makes emancipation possible. This then trickles to competence, and in the end it becomes a tool for them to turnaround household food security for the benefit of many. With its emphasis on competence despite exposure to adversity, the concept of resilience has long been attractive to applied practitioners seeking to promote strength in vulnerable individuals, groups, and societies. A wealth of research has documented processes by which individuals achieve positive developmental outcomes despite exposure to known threats to adaptation (Cicchetti, 2010)

Women's Coping Mechanisms Towards Household Food Security

Food Security has been a target of every nation as well as individual households in the world, Uganda inclusive (Bahiigwa 2002). Food production, household food security, has numerous challenges. Herein the researcher explores the coping mechanisms that women and other farmers have put in place so as to overcome those challenges. Some of those problems include inaccessibility to land and finances, and pests and diseases.

Women's Coping Mechanisms Towards Accessibility to Land and Finance

It is needless to emphasize on the significant contribution of women to agricultural production and household food security. Despite the fact that they produce more than half of all the food that is grown globally and up to 80% of basic foodstuffs in sub-Sahara Africa and the Caribbean, they do not have access to basic productive resources. Rural women who are obliged to attend to all the household chores, children's welfare, nutrition and family cohesion along with farm work, are desperately driven to adopt a survival strategy to save the family food security from total collapse (Prakash 1999). Furthermore, the use of rudimentary tools still accounts for more than 75 percent of Africa's food production. Agricultural extension strategies traditionally have focused on increasing production of cash crops by providing men with training, information, and access to inputs and services (Jiggins et al 2008). This has incapacitated women's efforts of food production; due to the fact that they don't have equal chances as those of men yet they are the main food producers.

To improve household food security, besides skills and knowledge, women require a natural and physical resource, such as land. Accessing land is an important prerequisite for both household food security and poverty reduction (UN Millennium Project 2005). Accessibility of land aids food production. FAO (2008) insists that 50% of the world's hungry are smallholder farmers, 20% are landless rural, 20% are pastoralists, fishers and forest dependent and 20% are the urban poor. Masuku and Sithole (2009) also found out that rural households with a sizeable amount of land are better off and are less likely to be poor and food-insecure than those with marginal lands or without land. Thus, women's accessibility to land and land reform in alleviating food insecurity is evidently indeed important. According to Masuku and Sithole (2009), the result of reforming landholding and access in China was a reduction in income-based absolute poverty to an average of approximately 6-11% from 1979 to 1981. There was also a sustained reduction in the number of the poor, from about 240 million to about 50 to 80 million, over the same period. Furthermore, the agricultural growth rate, crop yields and per capita food grain production rose substantially. The South Korean land reform programme also resulted in 60% increase of the total cultivated land area and a dramatic improvement in livelihoods. The average annual rate of food production increased by 4%; average farm income per household also increased by

51.4% between 1963 and 1975. Poverty reduced at a rate of 20% per decade between 1945 and 1950, and at 10% per decade from 1965 to 1978.

Natural and physical resources, like land, are almost entirely controlled by men (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). FAO studies confirm that while women are the mainstay of small-scale agriculture, the farm labor force and day-to-day family subsistence, they have more difficulties than men in gaining access to resources such as land, credit and productivity enhancing inputs and services (FAO 2010c). Throughout the developing world, with significant gaps in data, women control land and other productive resources less frequently than men do (UN Millennium Project 2005). Their rights, land 'rights', are usually only through a relationship with a man. If this relationship is ended, through divorce or death, women most often lose their right to the land (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). For food security, they ought to be protected from this discrimination (WFP 2009). UN Millennium Project (2005) states:

Men and women acquire land in many ways, through inheritance, purchase or transfers from the state (land reform programmes, resettlement schemes for people displaced by large dams and other projects, antipoverty programmes). Research shows that each channel of land ownership has a gender bias: male preference in inheritance, male privilege in marriage, gender inequality in the land market and male bias in state programmes of land administration.

Despite the critical role women play in food production and management of natural resources, they have ownership of only 1% of the land (ILO 2009). The strategies for increasing women's access to land ought to be specifically put in place. These strategies are needed to increase women's control over land, alongside with roads, water and livestock (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004, Tebajjukira 2010). The Millennium Project suggests these areas to be explored: reforming laws and supporting women's claims to property; joint [husbands and wives] titling; and collective approaches to support women's access to land (UN Millennium Project 2005).

Accessibility of land is tangible form of resource which helps women in the production of food and its security (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). In October 2001, at women's conference on land ownership in Africa, human rights activists warned: 'Africa is sinking into a food insecurity crisis because women, the main agricultural producers, are denied access and control of land' (WWAFC 2003). In Ethiopia, according to Fafchamps and Quisumbing (2005), where land reform has been part of the constitution since the 1960's, there is still wide variety in how women receive land, whether from inheritance, divorce, or the government. Girls still rarely inherit land from their parents, as do boys. Men control assets like land during the marriage and after (Fafchamps and Quisumbing 2005). In the cocoa growing regions of Ghana, according to Quisumbing, et al (2003), 'gift' transfers have become increasingly important as a means for women to acquire land for the establishment of cocoa farms. However, the 'gift' is easier for males to receive than females -men must plant only 20-25% of a parcel with cocoa trees to have the land transferred to them; whereas, women must plant 40-50% before acquiring the land as a 'gift'. Despite this inequity, the gift transfers have strengthened women's rights. Ugandan society is predominantly strongly patriarchal. Land ownership, access to land, access to other productive resources and the organization of agricultural production are influenced by cultural practices and traditions. For example, in many ethnic groups in Uganda, rules of land inheritance and access to land are culturally determined through lineage or gender. This has an impact on food production. Communally, household and individually-owned land, all determine what is produced and how it is distributed (Villarreal 2000).

On the same note, Uganda's Prime Minister, Apollo Nsibambi, speaking about land ownership reform to be included in the Domestic Relations Bill, encouraged women to challenge the 'die-hard patriarchal sociopolitical and economic structures which promote inequalities in land ownership' (WWAFC 2003). Tebajjukira (2010) reports a study by Action Aid that presented by the agency's policy manager -Paul Ojuman. This study revealed that women in Uganda lack access to productive land; even though 80% of them are engaged in agriculture. According to the report launched on Friday of 18th June 2010 at Hotel Africana in Kampala, although women constitute the majority of farmers producing most of the food in the country, lack of land discourages them from

diversifying into higher-value cash crops and investing in land improvements. According to the study conducted between August and November 2009, women own only 7% of productive land, which implies that men own 93% of agricultural land. The report reads: 'Women have limited access to economic opportunities primarily because they lack the assets and resources such as land and capital and because they are marginalised in decision-making over resource use'. The report, presented to MPs and NGO representatives, further noted that about 28% of house-holds are headed by women, of whom 69% are food insecure, due to limited access to land. This lack of control of an important productive resource, land in specific, significantly constrains women's productivity (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004).

To improve household food security, in addition to land, another resource needed by women is finance. Micro-finance programs, sometimes known as micro-credit and micro-enterprise programs, extend small loans and other financial services to poor people to generate self-employment. Microfinance programs often offer a combination of services and resources to their clients including saving facilities, training, networking, and peer support, so important to women (Katherine 2001). In spite of social, political and economic constraints, women farmers have proved extremely resourceful and hardworking in their attempt to ensure household food security. Social constraints place barriers around their access to scientific and technological information. Lack of collateral denies them access to agricultural credit (Prakash 1999).

Regarding ownership of land, we have established that women do not enjoy equal rights. This is worse particularly in the developing countries where most of the production, processing, storage and preparation of food are carried out by the women (UN Press Release 1998). Without title to land people generally, and women in particular, lack access to related essential resources such as credit, agricultural extension services, technical assistance and participation, new technologies and water rights (UN Millennium Project 2005, ILO 2009). This little access to credit limits their ability to purchase seeds, fertilizers and other inputs needed to adopt new farming techniques (Jiggins et al 2008). For example, if it is only 17% of Ugandan women who own registered land (Tebajjukira 2010), then accessing agricultural loans is indeed a problem for women. Tebajjukira (2010) records a discovery that only 10% of people engaged in agricultural activities are able to access agricultural loans. And most significantly, that only 9% of Ugandan women access such loans.

Since women produce half of the food grown (UN Press Release 1998), then their accessibility to finance is a significant key to achieving food security. Women play an indispensable role in farming and in improving food security. Emancipation of women, by strengthening their control over the asset base described above, has proved crucial for food security. As stated by the Deputy Secretary of the United Nations, Ismat Kittani at the UN World Conference on Women in Beijing: 'The challenge is how to make the existing laws take effect in the daily lives of women' (Plattner 1995). Their contributions often remain concealed due to some social barriers and gender bias. Equitable access for rural women to educational facilities, land and finance would certainly improve their performance and liberate them from their marginalized status in the society, so as to improve household food security. And it is in this regard that the researcher was to assess how women of Kalagala have coped with such inequitable access to resources.

In order to overcome the challenges of land and finance, women have resorted to social grouping. Social grouping is the quality of an individual's link to other individual/s and/or group/s. Women's groups are an example of social resource that has improved the status of women (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). From one another, they acquire skills and knowledge on food production and processing so as to improve household food security. These groups differ from each other in terms of purpose and capacities, as they are influenced by their environmental and socioeconomic conditions. Generally, objectives of women's groups include giving women equal access to and control of land and other productive resources, increasing their participation in decision-making and policy-making, reducing the workloads of women and enhancing their opportunities for paid employment and income.

It is noteworthy that, in terms of the ratio of membership of women in agricultural cooperatives, the percentage is rather low, yet, they have a strong influence on them and household food security. Certain obvious barriers restrict women's direct and formal entry in agricultural cooperatives. Even in countries like Japan, the ratio of

women membership in agricultural cooperative is extremely low (Prakash 1999). Women farmers and their groups, for example, have been key research partners in China. This has tremendous results. It has enhanced and integrated gender perspectives into various aspects of life. Throughout their meetings, women exchange many agricultural opinions, ideas and experiences. They have further enhanced their capacity for self-organization and management. They can also train in management, seed production and marketing; their access to seed market information has increased; and they are now becoming directly involved in the formal seed market. Moreover, these women have become more and more dynamic in their households and communities. They are playing a leading role in production and income-generating activities in terms of participation and decision making (CCAP 2003). In the absence of institutional support, some women farmers support each, for example, through the exchange of information, skills and experience; the sharing of labor; and setting up of and managing of micro-credit.

Besides accessibility of the knowledge and skills, good quality seeds are provided by the Guangxi Maize Research Institute and by experience women farmers, which has improved maize production (Song 1998, Song and Vernooy 2003). In workshops, training in seed production is carried out in the field by experienced women farmer, local extensionists and formal breeders (Song 1998). This has enhanced local seed systems and indigenous networks by adding value to farmers' knowledge and local processes, economically, culturally and socially. Women farmer groups also continue to be actively involved in the design and implementation of participatory plant breeding (PPB) field experiments. These strengthened groups provide support for farmers, especially women, by establishing and operating viable seed enterprises to improve incomes and livelihoods more broadly (CCAP 2003).

Women's groups, as coping mechanisms, have also enabled women to access market. Limited access to market affects food security, especial in Africa. This is Due to poor or lack of infrastructure such as roads, low capital base, limited access to information and poor government policies which make many small-scale farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa unable to market their produce away from their immediate neighborhood. For example, poor road networks prevent farmers from accessing target markets in time and in a cost-effective way, which would enable them to make a profit.

However, through social grouping, some efforts have been made to link the women farmers with the external seed market to add value to their product and empower them in the process (Song and Jiggins 2003). This has brought about women farmers' involvement in the market system, which ultimately empowers them economically and politically. As a result, the capabilities and bargaining power of the women in these groups have been strengthened. It also helps in building the capacity of the team and emancipating women farmers, which improved food security (Song 1998, CCAP 2003). Therefore, marginalized women farmers and their knowledge can be easily recognized, protected and strengthened through a collaborative process in which farmers and the researchers, extensionists and policy makers in the formal system work together on a more equal basis. In sum, strengthening women's groups (or other farmers' groups) can be the first step in self-organization and autonomous capacity building towards food security.

In their groups, women also share financial skills and experience; and enable them to access micro-credit. We have already established that without title to land women in particular lack access to important resources such as credit. So the emancipated women have grouped themselves so as to access such services. Micro-finance program is one type of financial capital program that works very well when administered through women's groups (Quisumbing and Meinzen-Dick 2004). As a result, FAO (2010e) encourages farmers in Central Uganda to join NAADS, SACCOs and LED as a solution to household food insecurity. Therefore, in connection with Kalagala women, the researcher intends to explore their challenges and subsequent coping mechanisms in regards to inaccessibility of land and finance.

Apart from social groupings women have resorted to entrepreneurship. In Uganda although women constitute a little over one half of her population, they rank slower than men in almost every social indicator in the country (UBOS, 2009). However despite this, female entrepreneurs are increasingly prominent as employers, customers, suppliers, and competitors in the global community. More than one third of the people involved in

entrepreneurial activities are women (GEM 2004). In addition, over the past fifteen years women's participation in economic activities has also moved beyond agriculture into the local market economy. In a research for wage employment, women are moving into small businesses and self employment ventures thereby creating many formal and informal opportunities for work. Women's participation in the informal sectors has increased significantly in both urban and rural areas. Vending, petty trade liquor making and vegetable selling are some of the common employment ventures undertaken by women (Snyder, 2000). It is therefore in this regard that the researcher investigated the coping mechanisms that the women of Kalagala have put in place to combat inaccessibility to Land and Finance.

Women's Coping Mechanisms on Crops Diseases and Pests

Several factors have been cited as possible reasons for vulnerability to food insecurity in Uganda. They include, unreliable rainfall patterns; declining soil fertility; pests and diseases; lack of access to land by some potential producers; low commodity prices; reliance on traditional methods of production (use of unimproved seeds and animal breeds and use of the hand hoe) and poor extension services (GOU 1998). With specific reference to Central Uganda, immediate causes of food insecurity include crop and livestock pests and diseases. This is as a result of high rainfall amounts and poor husbandry practices e.g. late planting, and no spraying of livestock feeds and livestock diseases, water logging and contamination of water sources and torrential rains and hailstorms (FAO 2010e).

Even drought resistant crops are greatly affected by pests and diseases. In Uganda, cassava crops are damaged by high levels of Cassava Mosaic Virus and this, compounded by poor agricultural practices and poorer soil, has led to food shortages (FAO/WFP 2004). Fungal and Bacterial crop diseases like banana bacterial wilt, root rots and blight are also common (FAO 2010e). An increase in livestock diseases associated with high rainfall e.g. calf scours, biting flies, liver flukes, and Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) lead to increased veterinary and drug costs resulting in a reduction in net income from livestock and related products (FAO 2010e). Generally, coping mechanisms on pests and diseases includes mixed farming, (Lanne and Thomas 2005a, Lanne and Thomas 2005b), organic methods (like clean planting materials, clean seeds, fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides, rotational farming, intercropping, mulching, closed seasons, fallowing, and paring) (http://www.appropedia.org/Pests_and_disease_control), and by planting pests and diseases resistant crops (Smale and Tushemereirwe 2007).

In Uganda, pests and diseases affects household food security. Uganda is Africa's leading producer and consumer of bananas. Highly cooking (*Musa* spp., genome group AAA-EA) and bear bananas (*Musa* spp., genome group AAA-EA, ABB and AB) comprise the staple food for Ugandans, especially for central region (Gold *et al.* 1999a). Yet, among the major constraints to highland cooking banana production in Uganda, for example, is the high level of pests. Most destructive ones are the banana weevil, *Cosmopolites sordidus* (Gold *et al.* 2001) and a complex of plant parasitic root nematodes (*Radopholus similis*, *Pratylenchus goodeyi* and *Helicotylenchus multicinctus*) (Gold *et al.* 2003). The adult banana weevil is black and measures 10-15 mm. It is free living, though most commonly found between leaf sheaths, in the soil at the base of the mat or associated with crop residues (Gold *et al.* 1997). The weevil is nocturnally active and very susceptible to desiccation. Although adults move freely within banana stands, few disperse more than 50 m in three months (Gold *et al.* 1999b). They rarely fly. Widespread infestation is caused primarily by movement of planting materials containing the pest in its immature stage and, occasionally, adult stages (Clifford 2003).

The effects of banana weevil and plant parasitic root nematodes on household food security, particularly in Uganda, are enormous. The adult weevil attack can prevent crop establishment (Price 1999), cause significant yield reductions in ratoon crops (Rukazambuga *et al.* 2000) and contribute to shortened plantation life (Gold *et al.* 1999a). To put it differently, banana weevil specifically attack has been reported to interfere with root initiation, kill existing roots, limit nutrient uptake, reduce plant vigour, delay flowering and increase susceptibility to other pests and diseases. These attack the root and corm, reducing the stability of the banana plant and interfering with the uptake of nutrients and water. Their combined damage results in plant loss through toppling and snapping reduced bunch weights and shortened plantation life. Tunneling by banana

weevil larvae weakens the plant and may even cause death of suckers, as well as snapping, toppling, deterioration of the root system, reduced nutrient uptake, smaller bunches, diminished vigor of followers and mat die-out (Gold *et al.* 2003). This increases household food insecurity, because yield reductions are caused by both plant loss (plant death, rhizome snapping, toppling) and lower bunch weights. Additionally, toppling, more commonly attributed to nematodes, has been observed under conditions of high weevil attack in the absence of nematodes (Gold *et al.* 1997; 2003).

Consequently, the weevil has been implicated as a primary factor in the decline and disappearance of highland cooking banana from its traditional growing areas in central Uganda (Gold *et al.* 1999a) and western Tanzania (Mbwana and Rukazambuga 1999). In a trial on highland banana in Uganda, Rukazambuga *et al.* (2000) findings showed that damage increased with crop cycle resulting in associated yield loss rising from 5% in the plant crop to 44% in the third ratoon. Gold *et al.* (2003) found out that the loss is more than 33% in weevil-infested plots six years after planting, compared to 5% in controlled conditions.

To cope up with the challenges associated with banana weevil and nematodes, farmers, women farmers inclusive, have come up with control strategies. At present, no single management strategy appears likely to provide complete control of banana weevil. Thus, a broad integrated pest management strategy has been employed. The components of such control include host plant resistance, cultural control, biological control (including microbial control) and chemical control. Firstly, in relation with host plant resistance, adult banana weevils are attracted by volatiles emanating from host plants. Cut rhizomes are especially attractive. Therefore, it can be difficult to establish a new crop in previously infested fields or near stands supporting heavy infestations. Banana weevils are attracted to cut rhizomes, making suckers used as planting material especially susceptible to attack. Loss of more than 40% of the plant crop to banana weevil has been recorded (Gold *et al.* 2003). Surveys and screening trials suggest that at least some clones in other genome groups are resistant or partially resistant to banana weevil (Kiggundu *et al.* 1999, Kiggundu 2000, Clifford 2003). Some of these might serve as parents in breeding programmes for weevil resistance. It is likely that many of the *Musa* cultivars are resistant or partially resistant to banana weevil. The banana weevil is readily attracted to and will freely oviposit on resistant clones (Clifford 2003). Furthermore, conventional breeding for pest resistance in banana is a long-term strategy; resistant clones may not satisfy consumer tastes. Therefore, there is increasing interest in breeding for banana weevil resistance by using biotechnology techniques. This would allow incorporation of resistant genes without changing other desirable properties in highland bananas and plantains. Many plants may fail to establish if planting is done in a previously infested field. So farmers have been strategically avoiding such fields.

Touching on cultural control of banana weevil and nematodes, farmers use clean planting material to reduce initial banana weevil infestation and retard pest build-up. The benefits of clean planting material are reduced when bananas are planted in proximity to infested fields that provide a source of weevils. Tissue culture is widely used in commercial banana plantations in Latin America, Asia and Africa for pest and disease control, but this method is beyond the reach of most small-scale farmers in much of Africa. Paring of the leaf sheaths and outer surface of the rhizome removes most weevil eggs and first instar larvae (Gold *et al.* 1999a). Hot-water treatment, widely promoted for weevil and nematode control, has only limited benefit as compared to paring for banana weevil. Farmers often immerse pared suckers in hot-water baths of 52-55°C for 15-27 minutes. These baths are very effective in eliminating nematodes, but kill only a third of the weevil larvae (Gold *et al.* 2003). To control banana weevils, farmers also have been trapping weevils. This reduces the populations of adult banana weevils. In Uganda particularly, after one year of pseudostem trapping, weevil populations declined by 61% in researcher managed fields (1 trap/mat/month), 43% in farmer-managed fields (0.3-0.6 traps/mat/month) and 23% in controls (Gold *et al.* 2003). However, trapping is labor demanding and often limited by available materials. Farmers have widely been practicing crop sanitation (i.e. destruction of residues) as a means of controlling weevils. It has been proposed that crop residues serve as a refuge and breeding ground for adult weevils, resulting in higher populations and increased damage. Thus, farmers do crop sanitation to eliminate weevil refuges and breeding sites and to reduce weevil numbers (Clifford 2003). Cultural control is very

valuable in preventing the establishment of the weevil and is the only means currently available by which resource-limited, small-scale growers can reduce established populations.

As another coping mechanism emancipated women farmers use biological control, arthropod natural enemies of banana weevils so as to secure enough food for household members. Since banana weevil is an exotic pest in Africa and Latin America, farmers have resorted to classical biological control. The natural enemies that African farmers have introduced include *myrmicine* ants, *parasitoids* and *predators*, as effective biological control agents. Myrmicine ants are widespread in East Africa banana systems. In Kenya, *endemic* natural enemies of banana weevil (*histerids*, *hydrophilids*, *staphylinids* and *earwigs*) appear to offer limited promise (Koppenhofer *et al.* 2000). The potential of biological control in highland banana systems is currently limited. The natural enemies attack both adults and larvae in the field, but economic cost and efficacy only under high weevil population densities limit their use on a larger scale for the moment (Waterhouse and Norris 1997, Nankinga 2002).

Closely related to biological control, farmers have employed *microbial* control as a coping strategy towards securing enough bananas for household members. Microbial control of banana weevil and nematodes has been reviewed by Gold *et al.* (2001, 2003) and Niere (2001). According to Griesbach (2000), Nankinga (2002) and Gold *et al.* (2003) microbial agents used against banana weevils include entomopathogenic fungi (e.g. *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae*) and nematodes (e.g. *Steinernema* spp. and *Heterorhabditis* spp.) are mostly used to kill adult weevils; while endophytes (e.g. non-pathogenic *Fusarium* spp.) effectively control the immature stages of the pest. The use of endophytic fungi is a novel yet promising control strategy that can be used against the banana weevil (Griesbach 2000) and parasitic nematodes (Niere 2001). For example, Griesbach (2000) reported increased banana biomass production in field plants of the cultivars Nakyetengu and Nfuuka inoculated with the fungal endophyte *Fusarium concentricum*. Although the nematodes are able to reduce weevil numbers, they are not economically competitive with pesticides making microbial control less effective (Treverrow 1999, Griesbach 2000, Gold *et al.* 2003).

Additionally, financially able farmers have employed chemical control as a coping strategy towards securing enough bananas particularly for commercial purposes. Farmers use nematicides with insecticidal activity and specific insecticides, like cyclodiene, applied close to the base of the mat. Insecticides are fast acting and efficient. But the banana weevil has now shown the ability to develop resistance to most classes of chemicals. So farmers use botanical compounds to serve as substitutes for pesticides. They dip suckers in a 20% neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seed solution at planting that serves to protect the young suckers from weevil attack by reducing *oviposition* through its repellent effect on adult weevils. Egg eclosion rates is also lowered in neem-treated plants (Ogenga-Latigo and Bakyalire 1999; Gold *et al.* 1999b, Gold *et al.* 1999c, Gold *et al.* 1999d). Therefore, farmers, including women farmers, have integrated control strategies as coping mechanisms towards securing enough bananas for household members. To cope up with the challenges associated with banana weevil and nematodes, they have employed various pest management strategies. These include: host plant resistance, cultural control, biological control, microbial control and chemical control. The researcher was therefore compelled to examine how Kalagala women are coping with pests and diseases especially on bananas in their fight against household food insecurity.

How Women Emancipation Equips Them with Skills and Knowledge to Improve Household Food Security

Food security is a multi-dimensional development issue that needs cross-sectoral integrated approaches. Among several ways that should be employed to curb the problem of food insecurity is empowering women. This was looked at by assessing the equipment of women with resources, knowledge and skills to help them in fighting food insecurity in the area. Putting it differently the researcher wanted to know if after being empowered, women appreciated the fact that they needed to own or to access land in order to grow crops and raise animals for food security; appreciate the importance of having access to tools and other equipments for land preparation; familiar of the land act and domestic bill so that they are aware of laws governing property ownership in the home; whether they are aware of methods of cooking local foods in order to retain the needed nutrients. The researcher

also wanted to gauge whether women had had trainings in various enterprises to help them produce food in the home and whether they can carry out post-harvest processing and value addition in the various agricultural food products. The researcher therefore sought to use both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection to examine if the type of empowerment women of Kalagala sub-county receive equips them with skills and knowledge to improve household food security.

One of the important resources used in food production is land. The researcher wanted to find out if and how women owned land on which they practiced food production. Results are shown in Table 8 and figure

Table 1: Ownership of land for farming

Land ownership in the home	Frequency	Percent
Land is owned by the Community	27	8
My in-laws own the land	24	7
My husband owns the land	198	56
We jointly own the land with my husband	14	4
I personally own the land	88	25
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

According to Table 8 and figure 2, majority of respondents (56%) revealed that they farm on their husbands' land, 25% used their personal land, 8% farm on land they referred to as 'communal land' which, in this case was land put aside by a clan or close group for members to use for food production. Another 7% indicated they farmed on land that belongs to their in-laws, while 4% used land jointly owned by the husband and wife. The results are also reflected in Figure 2 below.

Figure 1: Ownership of land for farming

On the question of whether women emancipation equipped them with skills to combat food insecurity, the researcher tried to find out specific enterprises in which respondents had had training. Results are shown in Table 11 and figure 3.

Table 2: Enterprises in which respondents have had training

Enterprises respondents had had training	Frequency	Percent
Vegetable nursery planting and management	20	6
Mushroom growing	7	2
Local chicken rearing	85	24
Dairy farming	74	21
None	165	47
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Majority of respondents (47%) indicated that they have had no training in skills acquisition at all, while 24% indicated they trained in local chicken rearing. About 21% indicated that they had had training in dairy farming, while 6 % indicated they trained in local vegetable nursery planting and management. Only 2% indicated they trained in mushroom growing. When interviewed, nearly all of the respondents said that, most of the trainings took place far from the villages and so they could not access them.

The researcher tried to find out about the farming methods respondents used on their farms.

The results revealed that, according to the respondents, 85% of them were not using new farming methods, in contrast to 15% who claimed to use new methods. However, it was evident that none of the interviewed people used new farming techniques of production like tractors for ploughing spraying, fertilizers or even ox-ploughs.

The researcher also wanted to find out whether respondents were aware of the various laws and rules in the country for the emancipation of women. This was asked in terms of awareness of the New Land Act of 1998 and Domestic Relations Bill. The results are presented in Table 9.

Table3: Access to cultivation implements, knowledge of land amendment bill and, domestic relations bill

N=351 Responses	No		Yes	
	F	%	F	%
Have access to land cultivation implements like ox plough, disc plough	299	85	52	15
Heard of the new Land Act of 1998 or Land Amendment Act (2009)?	159	45	192	55
Heard of the Domestic Relations Bill?	107	31	244	70

Source: Field Data (2011)

The results indicated that 55% of the respondents revealed that they were aware of the New Land Act while 45% had not heard of it; 70% had heard of the Domestic Relations Bill while 30% claimed not to have heard of it. The study revealed that 65% of the respondents who were aware of the Domestic Relations Bill said it could help them acquire properties like registered land while 25% were not sure whether the Bill would be of help to them.

In light of skills and knowledge acquisition by emancipated women, the researcher also tried to find out about methods of cooking food used by the respondents. This was in view of the fact that the method of cooking can destroy available nutrients from a food stuff rendering it useless to the one who eats it. Results are shown in Table 10.

Table 4: Cooking Methods for some common Local Foods

N=351 Cooking methods	Steaming		Boiling		Frying		Roasting	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
How do you normally cook vegetables for eating?	184	52	120	34	41	12	6	2
How do you normally cook Matoke, potatoes and cassava for eating?	284	81	64	18	3	1	0	0
How do you normally cook meat for eating?	39	11	257	73	44	13	11	3

Source: Field Data (2011)

In reference to the methods used by the respondents to cook local foods, (Table 11), it was that 52% of the respondents used steaming as a way of cooking vegetables, 34% used boiling as a method of cooking

vegetables, 12% fried their vegetables. However, 2% cited roasting as a method although upon further questioning they couldn't name any vegetable roasted before eating it. Majority of the respondents interviewed said that usually, they didn't have cooking oil and therefore used steaming as the only option for cooking their vegetables, where upon they tied vegetables in banana leaves and covered them with yet larger banana leaves on top of 'matooke', sweet potato or cassava to be steamed.

From the same table, it was revealed that 81% of the respondents used steaming as a method of cooking their 'Matooke' (plantains), sweet potatoes and cassava, 18% used the boiling method and only 1% used frying method in cooking food stuffs like cassava and potatoes; though usually this is eaten as a snack.

When asked how they cooked meat, 73% of the respondents stated that they boiled it, 13% said they fried it, 11% steamed and only 3% said they roasted the meat.

Figure 2: The enterprises in which respondents have had training

Source: Field Data (2011)

On the same point about skills acquisition, the researcher tried to find out if respondents had any skills about post-harvest activities carried out on certain food stuffs they produced. Results are shown in table 12.

Table 5: Post-harvest processes and Value addition done on maize and other crops

Post-harvest activities on maize and sorghum	F	%	Value addition activities carried out on various types of foods	F	%
Store maize in the store or in a crib (still on the cob)	51	15	Cut cassava, dry and grind unto flour	82	23
Shell and Sell maize seed immediately	36	10	Turn fruits (like pineapples) into jam	24	7
Store maize seed in sacks in the house	228	65	Grind maize into flour	242	69
Grind sorghum into flour	36	10	Make tomato sauce from tomatoes	1	0.1
			Steam cowpeas leaves, dry and grind unto flour	2	1
Total	351	100	Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Results in Table 12 revealed that maize was shelled and the seed stored in sacks in the houses with 65% of the respondents confirming this, 15% stored maize in cribs, 10% shelled and sold the maize seed immediately, while another 10% indicated they ground sorghum into flour. Observations showed that women did not have stores and because of that they only had few alternatives like storing maize seed in sacks in their houses or grinding maize into flour before selling.

On the question of value addition activities done on various food crops, 69% of the respondents indicated they ground the maize into flour, 23% cut cassava, dried and ground it into flour. Another 7% indicated they turned fruit like pineapples into jam and only 1% indicated they steamed cowpeas, dried it and ground it into flour. None of the respondents made tomato sauce from fresh tomatoes. When interviewed, most of the respondents said that they lacked knowledge and skills to carry out value addition activities on various crops they produced on their farms.

As part of imparting skills and knowledge into rural women, the National Agricultural Research Organization (NARO), has involved women into collaborative research with breeders from National Agricultural Crop Resource Research Institute (NaCRRI) in Namulonge. The research sought to find out which of the women groups had involved themselves in research and which crops they participated in breeding. Results are shown in Table 13 below.

Table 6: Activities researched on by respondents in collaboration with Namulonge or Kawanda.

Crops involved in collaborative research with NARO	Frequency	Percent
Cassava growing	25	76
Banana growing	2	6
Upland rice	6	18
Total	33	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

The results in Table 6 show that 76% of the respondents, who were involved in research with NaCRRI, indicated that they did it in cassava growing, 18% in upland rice and 6% engaged in banana growing.

Women Emancipation and Attitude towards Household Food Security

Attitudes toward changing roles for women have been the subject of numerous recent studies and therefore the researcher was assessing whether emancipated women had developed a positive attitude towards agricultural productivity, hence household food security. Respondents were subjected to questions whose answers would indicate whether they were emancipated and whether they had a changed attitude towards household food security. Results are shown in Table 14 and figure 4.

Table 7: Whose responsibility it is to provide food for household members

Responsible Person	Frequency	Percent
Husband	57	16
Wife	288	82
Elder Children	6	2
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

In reference to whose responsibility it was to provide the family with food, 82% of the respondents insisted that it was the responsibility of the wife (women), 16% said it was the men's, and 2% said it was the elder mature children's responsibility to provide for the family. Accordingly, interviews also revealed that women did a lot in the provision of food in their households and therefore regarded men as dependants. As one respondent put it "*Children don't ask their father for food, and even when there is nothing to eat, the man also expects me to bring food*".

Figure 3: Whose responsibility to provide food for household members

Source: Field Data (2011)

Still on the question of attitude towards food production, respondents were asked about their attitude towards enjoyment of farming, whether they would re-invest money into farming, whether they would encourage their children to train in an agricultural profession and whether educated women should engage in food production. Results are presented in Table 15.

Table 8: Attitude of Women Towards Agricultural Productivity

Questions to probe attitude of respondents	No		Yes		Total
	F	%	F	%	
Do you enjoy your work in the garden?	17	5	334	95	100
In case of an improved income, is it advisable to invest more money in food production?	93	26	258	74	100
Would you like your children to train in Agricultural profession?	44	13	307	87	100
Could you advice the educated woman (diploma or degree holder) to engage in food production?	40	11	311	89	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Results show that 95% of the respondents indicated that they enjoyed work in the garden, while only 5% indicated they didn't. and 4% indicated that in case of improved income, they would invest more money in food production, while 87% indicated that they would encourage their children to train in an agricultural profession. Another 89% indicated they would advise educated women to engage in food production.

The researcher further sought to find out where the respondents could invest money if not on agricultural productivity. The results are presented in Table 16

Table 9: Where to invest money if not on agricultural productivity

Alternative Activities for Investment other than Food Production	Frequency	Percent
I would start a small shop	73	73
I would engage in mobile market selling old clothes	9	9
I would start buying food items to take to Kampala markets like Owino	13	13
I would start a saloon in the trading centre	5	5
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

The results in Table 16 show that 73% of the respondents who would not invest money in agricultural production indicated that they would rather invest in starting small shops, 13% would start buying food items and taking them to Kampala markets like Owino, 9% in mobile markets selling old clothes and 5% would start saloons in the nearby trading centers.

The researcher also tried to find out the reasons as to why the respondents would not want their children to train in agricultural profession. The results are presented in table 17

Table 10: Reasons for not having children train in agriculture

Reasons Given	Frequency	Percent
I would rather have him or her train in computer science	12	28
It is better he or she trains in medical profession	23	53
Agriculture does not pay well	6	13
Agriculture is for those who are not highly educated	3	6
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Out of all respondents, 13% had indicated that they could not advise their children to take agricultural profession. They gave reasons for not doing so as shown in Table 17. Majority of them (53%) indicated that they could rather have their children training in medical profession, 28% in computer science, and 13% insisted that Agriculture does not pay well and 6% indicated that Agriculture was for those who were not highly educated. Similar answers were given by those who were interviewed. From the interviews, it was evident that those women who didn't advocate for educated women to take up food production thought that it was for people with lower education standards while others were of the view that farming was tiring and dirty. Yet others thought that such educated people should get well-paid office jobs.

Women's Coping Mechanisms Towards Household Food Security

The researcher wanted to find out the coping mechanisms that emancipated women have put in place to combat household food security. The questions asked focused on women's coping mechanisms in acquiring extra income for funds to put into food production, joining societies and other bodies to help them produce more food and how they were coping to control banana bacterial wilt disease and banana weevils in the most important crop grown in the study area. One of the coping mechanisms was for the women to form women groups. When asked reasons for doing so the answers are portrayed in Table 18.

Table 11: Reasons for joining women groups

Reasons Given	Frequency	Percent
One learns a lot by joining such groups	54	16
It is easier to market produce in a group	46	13
I enjoy networking with fellow members	18	5
As a group we easily access a financial aid	233	66
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

The results in Table 18 show that 66% of respondents indicated that they joined women groups because they could easily access financial aid. 16% of the respondents indicated that they learnt a lot by joining such groups,

13% indicated it was easier to market their produce, while 5% indicated they enjoyed networking with fellow members.

Another way of coping with food insecurity was for the women to engage themselves into National Agricultural Advisory Services (NAADS) activities and Savings and Credit Co-operative Organizations (SACCO) activities in the study area. The respondents were asked if their groups were involved in NAADS and SACCO and if so what advantages they had obtained from them.

Table 12: Involvement in NAADS and SACCO activities in the study area

Questions about NAADS and SACCOs	No		Yes	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Is your association in NAADS?	98	28	253	72
Has NAADS helped you to increase household food security?	124	35	227	65
Does your group participate in research in collaboration with NARO (Namulonge or Kawanda)?	318	91	33	9
Does your women group have a SACCO where they save and borrow money?	20	6	331	94
Have you ever borrowed money from your SACCO?	33	9	318	91

Source: Field Data (2011)

The results from this study show that 72% of the respondents indicated that their social groups were involved in NAADS activities, while the remainder (28%) were not in association with NAADS. It further revealed that 65% of the respondents indicated that NAADS helped them in starting and improving farming activities like poultry farming, pig rearing and maize and beans production, as a way of improving household food security. Results also showed that 94% of the respondents had formed SACCOs where they would save and borrow money from. Of those who had SACCOs, 91% of them indicated that they had ever borrowed money from the SACCOs.

The respondents were given a list of enterprises to indicate the ones which they might have engaged in through NAADS programme and the results are shown in Table 20.

Table 13: Enterprises engaged in by respondents in association with NAADS

Enterprise engaged in	Frequency	Percent
Those who were not engaged in any enterprise	97	28
Poultry production	17	5
Piggery	16	5
Bee keeping	9	3
Maize and beans production	210	60
Dairy production	2	1
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Results show that 60% of the respondents involved themselves in maize and beans production, while 28% indicated they didn't engage in any enterprise with NAADS. Results also show that 5% in poultry production, 5% in piggery, 3% in bee keeping and 1% in dairy production.

In addition, respondents said that whenever their groups converged for meetings, they involved themselves in various activities like mat making, basketry and singing for income generation. Some of the women groups moved around in the village and contracted farm jobs like weeding, land preparation and harvesting on peoples' farms as a way of bringing income into their groups.

The researcher sought to know other sources of income for the respondent in regards to coping up with food insecurity in their households. Results are put forth in table 21

Table 14: Other sources of income for women in the respondents' village

Other sources of income given	Frequency	Percent
Farming in the home garden	271	77
Petty trading in food market	73	21
Engaged in mobile market	1	1
Selling in the kiosk in the trading centre	4	1
Money obtained from relatives abroad	2	1
Total	351	100

Source: Field Data (2011)

Table 21 shows that 77% of the respondents indicated that many do farming in the home garden as another source for income, 21% indicated that they do Petty trading in food market, while 1% could sell in kiosks in the nearby trading centers, and 1% get money from their relatives abroad and another 1% mobile marketing.

Furthermore, the study assessed the coping mechanisms through the control measures women have put in place to cope up with banana weevil. The respondents were requested to rank them according to their effectiveness and the results are drawn in Table 22

Table 15: Ranking control measures for banana weevil

Control measures of banana weevil	Mean
Plant bananas in fresh plot not previously grown bananas	1.51
Laying traps for weevil after harvesting	1.68
Chopping pseudo stem and stem after harvest	2.05
Immerse suckers in insecticide or hot water before planting	1.65
Apply biological insecticide (<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> or <i>Bacillus thuriangiensis</i>) or banana stool	2.19
Apply furadan (insecticide) to the stool	1.70

Source: Field Data (2011)

Key

1.00-1.700- not effective

1.80-2.40- less effective

2.50-3.10= effective

3.20-4.00-very effective

On ranking the control measures of banana weevil the results showed that Planting bananas in fresh plot not previously grown bananas was rated as not effective at 1.57, Immersing suckers in insecticide or hot water before planting at 1.65, Laying traps for weevil after harvesting at 1.68 and Applying furadan to the stool at 1.70.

Those which were rated as less effective were Chopping pseudo stem and stem after harvest at 2.05 and Applying biological insecticide (*Beauveria bassiana* or *Bacillus thuriangiensis*) or banana stool at 2.19.

None of the control measures was rated effective, this might be attributed to the fact that many of the methods used just worked for a while, or sometimes they failed to work. At the same time, banana weevil is still rampant despite the fact that many of these methods have been used.

Additionally, the researcher assessed the coping mechanism put in place by the respondents to control banana bacteria wilt disease. Table 23 illustrates the results.

Table 16: Coping up with banana bacteria wilt (BBW) disease

Activity done to control BBW	Frequency	Percent
I cut off the male bud when the banana is still young	111	32
I rouge and bury affected plants	189	54
I get planting suckers from healthy plantations	43	12
I plant resistant varieties like FHIA 17 (Kabana 3)	8	2
Total	351	100

Source:Field Data (2011)

The results in Table 23 show that 54% of the respondents indicated that they rouged and buried affected plants as a coping mechanism towards banana bacteria wilt disease, 32% cut off the male bud when the banana was still young, and 12% got planting suckers from healthy plantations and 2% planted resistant varieties like FHIA 17 (Kabana 3).

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, we have described the paradox that lies in the fact that the number of those threatened by food insecurity is increasing despite international pledges to “end hunger.” Although national governments acknowledge the need for food self-sufficiency, most of the women continue to be marginalized as assets, information, and technology pass into the hands of the financially and politically powerful. Male-dominated power structures fail to relate to women at a time of acclaimed acknowledgement of the latter’s contribution to agricultural, specifically food, production. At the household level, women lack access to productive technology. At the institutional and national levels, policies continue to discriminate against women in terms of access to and control over land technology, credit, markets, and so forth. Determining how to build on and use women’s knowledge base so that modern technologies can benefit from it and strengthen women’s efforts remains a problem. Therefore the researcher recommends the following:

- More women should be exposed to the Land Act 1998 and to the Domestic Bill. This should be done by the Ministry of Lands holding workshops and seminars through local leaders in the villages as a way Service of empowering them.
- The providers in NAADS and NGOs should train women on post harvest management and value addition for food preservation and better prices when selling so that it will help them in coping with household food insecurity. These trainings should include practical sessions on value addition for example jam making and wine production. This can be done every after three months to ensure full empowerment of women in this particular area.
- Women should be trained in running better paying enterprises especially those that need less land and capital outlay like mushroom growing, local chicken rearing and full courses should be offered to the same by Agricultural economists and agribusiness service providers.
- The NGOs and Agribusiness service providers should give women intensive training on credit management, project management and marketing for profitability. At least annually to ensure full course offerings.
- There should also be training on nutrition and healthy eating to the women by nutritionists, home economists and Primary care workers so that household food security can be achieved in terms of quantity and quality.
- Irrigation should be started so as to enable all year round farming so that there are no months without food in the homes. This can be done by agricultural engineers who should emphasize low-cost irrigation methods to the women.
- Food storage units in the form of cribs and granaries should be built at village level by the women helped by service providers from NAADS so that it can help women in storing their food instead of selling them. It will also help them to store their food throughout the year.

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